

A Study to Assess the Level of Medication Health Literacy among Patients with Coronary Artery Disease

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ABSTRACT

Many medical conditions can be treated or prevented with medication, resulting in a dramatic increase in medication use over the last few decades. Health literacy is an individual's ability to obtain and understand basic health information and services needed to make appropriate decisions regarding their health. Objective of the study was to assess the level of medication health literacy among patients with coronary artery disease visiting the outpatient department. Quantitative research approach is used to assess the level of medication literacy and among patients with coronary artery disease. 160 coronary artery disease patients were selected. Non probability convenience sampling technique used for the data collection. Data was collected by Medication Health literacy structured questionnaires to assess the medication Health literacy. Results shows that Most of participants had marginal literacy (74.4%) followed by higher literacy (38%) and then low literacy (1.9%) among participants.

KEY WORDS: Medication literacy, Coronary Artery Disease, Co-Morbidity, Outpatient Department, Health.

INTRODUCTION:

Many medical conditions can be treated or prevented with medication, resulting in a dramatic increase in medication use over the last few decades. People are also living longer, due to advance in medication knowledge, which means that many are living with multiple Co- morbidities and or taking multiple medication. Early mortality arising from cardiac disease can be reduced through the use of medications but medication adherence is often poor .This is influenced by many factors including health literacy. According to estimate world health organization almost 20.1 million adults age more than 20 and older have CAD about 72%. Adherence to therapy is a primary determinant of treatment success.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher has adopted Non- experimental Descriptive Research Design to assess the level of medication health literacy among coronary artery patients. The study has been conducted in the

outpatient department of super speciality hospitals. The hospitals were situated in the urban area. The reason for selecting these hospitals is administrative support and co-operation, availability of samples, convenience for transportation. The population of the present study was patients with coronary artery disease visiting outpatient department of super specialty hospital. Total 160 cases included in present study.

RESULT:

Description of samples based on their socio demographic variables in terms of frequency and percentage.

The mean score of age of participants $52.6 \text{ years} \pm 9.5$. Majority that is 83 (51.9%) participants visiting outpatients department were in age group of 46-60 years.

Regarding educational level of coronary artery patients majority of 82(51.3%) completed secondary education, 5(3.1%) of them had no formal education, 39(24.4%) of patients completed primary education and 34(21.3%) of completed graduation.

ANALYSIS OF DATA RELATED TO THE MEDICATION HEALTH LITERACY AMONG PATIENTS WITH CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE VISITING THE OUT PATIENT DEPARTMENT.

Medication health literacy among patients with coronary artery disease visiting the outpatient department.

Literacy	Freq	%
Inadequate literacy	3	1.9%
Marginal literacy	119	74.4%
Adequate literacy	38	23.8%

The table shows that analysis of medication literacy score among coronary artery disease reveal that 119 (74.4%) patients had marginal medication literacy score, and 38(23.8) had adequate level of medication literacy, along with 3(1.9%) of patients had inadequate level of medication literacy score.

DISCUSSION:

Based on analytical results found that 160 patients were participated in this study. In this present study according to section first data analyzed based on their socio- demographical variables. Results show that majority of 83(51.9%) coronary artery disease patients belongs to age group between 46 to 60 years. Finding of studies done in mid western state yen - mine Huang (2018) that majority 957.5%) patients belonged to age group between 46-60 years. Research study also shows the same results as present study.

Research result shows that analysis of medication literacy score among coronary artery disease reveal that 119 (74.4%) patients had marginal medication literacy score, and 38(23.8) had adequate level of medication literacy, along with 3(1.9%) of patients had inadequate level of medication literacy score. Researcher advice that need to focus on the patients education related to benefits of medication knowledge about their prescribe medication etc.

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- Majority 81(50.6%) of patients did not know the names of their medicines accurately, followed by 29(18.1%) of patients know partially accurate name of their medicines and 50(31.3%) of them know the names of all their medicines accurately.
- Majority 76(47.5%) of patients know the partially accurate purpose of their medicines, 58(36.3%) of patients know purpose of all their medicines and the action of each of their medicines accurately, and 26(16.3%) of them did not know the purpose of all their medicines.
- Majority 126(78.8%) of patients did not know the strengths of their medicines, 18(11.3%) of them partially accurately know the strengths of their medicines, and 16(10.0%) of patients accurately know the strengths of their medicines respectively.
- Majority 94(58.8%) of coronary artery disease patients accurately knew the dosage regimen of all their medicines, 64(40.0%) of them partially accurately know the dosage regimen of their medicines and 2(1.3%) of patients did not know the dosage regimen of all their medicines at all.
- Majority of 80(50.0%) of coronary artery patients partially accurately know major side effects of their all medicines, 3(8.1%) of patients accurately knew the major side effects of all their medicines, and 67(41.9%) of patients did not know the major side effects of all their medicines at all.
- Majority 146(91.3%) of patients accurately know the person to seek help when in doubt about medicines, 14(8.8%) of patients partially accurately know the person to seek help when in doubt about medications.

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CONCLUSION

It is generally thought that medication adherence will be improved with medication literacy, but as findings suggested that it does not have any impact on patient medication adherence. Apart from no association between medication literacy and adherence, researcher also found that there are several socio demographic factors may influence the level of adherence and patient's medication literacy. It suggests that other than patient education, measures are required in order to improve the adherence of patient in long term medication regimen.

KEYWORDS:

Medication literacy, medication adherence, coronary artery disease, co-morbidity, impact